

IMPROVING THE PROTECTION OF POPULATIONS AND TERRITORIES FROM THE EARTHQUAKE AND ITS SECONDARY CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. This article comments on improving the protection of the population and territories from the earthquake and its secondary consequences. The measures used to protect the population in an emergency situation, to avoid the unpleasant consequences of this phenomenon or to reduce it to the maximum are complex measures.

Key words: natural, earthquake, Earth, relative, seismic, shaking, safety.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ И ТЕРРИТОРИЙ ОТ ЗЕМЛЕТРЯСЕНИЯ И ЕГО ВТОРИЧНЫХ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЙ

Аннотация. В этой статье даны отзывы об улучшении защиты населения и территорий от землетрясения и его вторичных последствий. Меры, применяемые для защиты населения в условиях чрезвычайной ситуации, предотвращения или максимального снижения неблагоприятных последствий данного явления, являются комплексными.

Ключевые слова: природный, землетрясение, земля, относительный, сейсмический, сотрясение, безопасность.

Natural disasters are considered to be destructive events to the ecological environment, the national economy, causing severe disasters to the head of humanity, and occur in different forms every year in different regions of our country. For example: it is no secret that flooding in the regions of the Fargona Valley, flooding in the regions of Khorezm and Tashkent, and dust-dust winds in the regions of Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya, Afghan winds are causing threatening situations. Of the natural phenomena, the most devastating are earthquakes in large areas, which cause much damage to Nature, Society and the ecological state. Throughout its entire historical development, humanity has experienced many earthquakes, witnessing its consequences. A long historical lesson, that is, the impact of the Earth's shaking on the mental state of people, the destruction, destruction of buildings and structures, the changes that occurred on the surface of the Earth have established an assessment of the strength of the phenomenon in which cracks and springs occur at the ground level.

The result was a relativistic assessment seismic scale. Below we will outline this relative seismic scale with some variations. In our republic and in many states, the strength of an earthquake is estimated on a scale of 12 points, and an earthquake with each Score has its own detail. In addition the assessment also uses the 8-point Richter seismic scale.

We have mainly observed 2 types of landslides:

- long period lasting 1.5-2.5 minutes;
- high frequency oscillation lasting 1.5-2.5 seconds.

In long-period landslides, vibration slowly builds up strength, and it is considered dangerous for high-rise buildings. Due to the separation of high-frequency earthquake energy within a short period, the consequences can be sad, the reason being that if slow motion can lead to much sacrifice. The main indicators of the Earth's tremor are the depth of the center of the tremor and how long the vibration is repeated. Its impact strength on the Earth's surface, as described above, is usually estimated in points.

Below we explain this relative seismic scale with some variations:

1. ball is recorded without sensations-only on seismic instruments.
2. ball can be noticed by some people sitting inside a very weak house (the window panes tremble).

3. the score is weak, most people do not notice, a person standing still in the open air can notice. Hanging bodies oscillate gradually.

4. points are noticeable on average. People standing in the open air and people inside the building will notice. The walls of the House are wrinkled. Fasting utensils vibrate, hanging bodies vibrate.

5. points are much stronger. Everyone will notice, the sleeping person will swallow.

Some people run out into the yard. The liquid in the container is splashed and spilled, the hanging household appliances vibrate strongly.

6. the ball is strong, everyone notices, the sleeping person wakes up. Most people run out into the yard, the pets are unattended. In some cases, books from the bookshelf, dishes from the shelves will turn over.

7. the score is very strong. Many people are overwhelmed by fear, run out into the street, are also noticed by motorists during Movement, large cracks appear on the walls of the house, the waters in the basins are splashed and blurred.

8. ball Destroyer. unripe brick structures are completely destroyed, much more mature structures also develop cracks, moors at the top of the House are knocked down, some trees fall with their entire bodies, break, collapse in the Highlands, creep events occur.

9. ball wrecker. Structures and structures that are designed to withstand landslides are also heavily damaged, can slip from foundations and become crooked, ordinary buildings are completely destroyed, cracks appear on the surface of the Earth, groundwater can leak out.

10. ball taker. All buildings see great damage. The rail rails enter a wavy shape and bend to one side.

The effectiveness of population protection can only be achieved if all available tools and methods are fully worked out and the principles of safety protection are fully realized.

According to the application of the principles of ensuring safety, it is divided into three groups:

1. Prepare in advance (personal and collective), collect protective equipment, keep them ready and prepare activities for the evacuation of the population from the danger area UA implementation.

2. The nature of the size of differentiated orientation measures is dangerous, and the type of source of toxic factors depends on local conditions.

3. Effective use of methods and means of protection against the consequences of the complex of events, accompanied by activities to ensure the safety of vital activity in a modern techno-social environment.

An earthquake is a natural disaster caused by the displacement of moving plates on Earth. There are many secondary effects of an earthquake, and these effects may require a number of measures to protect the population and the region.

People directly affected by the earthquake event may lose their homes, jobs, and other assets. In addition, there may also be people who lost their lives or were injured during this disaster. In addition, infrastructure damage, water supply pollution, and power lines may be damaged in the area affected by the call. All of these situations can pose a potential threat to the safety and well-being of morality.

Some measures can be taken to protect the population and borders. First of all, it is necessary to consider the construction and settlements in the earthquake regions and carry out the necessary activities. Strengthening works can be carried out to increase the durability of buildings and necessary measures can be taken to make the buildings suitable for use after an earthquake.

It is also important that emergency teams and their resources are ready in the area. For rapid response, training and equipment of emergency teams must be strengthened. In addition, local residents must be informed of the correct behavior and emergency plans. In this way, it can be ensured that people are aware of how they should act in the event of an earthquake.

Infrastructure strengthening work must also be carried out at the same time to reduce the secondary impact of the call. Critical infrastructure elements such as water resources, power lines, and communications infrastructure must be ring resistant. In addition, cleaning and maintenance work after the disaster should also be carried out quickly.

Finally, scientific research should also be carried out to assess the risk of measles in the region and predict possible effects. Thus, it is possible to take more effective measures to reduce the risk of earthquakes, better maintain morals and boundaries.

When solving the problem under these conditions, a comprehensive approach is needed to ensure the safety of people in emergency situations, covering the issues of reducing the likelihood of risk prevention and occurrence, as well as reducing the size of its consequences. On this methodological basis, taking into account the experience of our own UA foreign practice, it is necessary to prepare in advance a complex of activities that will justify the ever-increasing efficiency, in other words, to introduce a multi-layered system of ensuring the safety of people in a modern techno-social environment.

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